

ADHESIVE INTERACTIONS IN INTERPHASES: COMPETITION BETWEEN ACID-BASE AND DIFFUSION MECHANISMS

Elena Pisanova, Serge Zhandarov, and Edith Mäder

*Institute of Polymer Research
Hohe Str. 6, Dresden 01069, Germany*

SUMMARY: Bond strength between reinforcing fibers and polymer matrices can be controlled in two ways: 1) by intensification of molecular interaction at the interface and 2) by creation of a strong continuous layer (interphase) between the components. In this paper, we consider the possibilities of controlling interfacial strength by means of target-oriented variation of structure, thickness and strength of the interphase artificially created between the fiber and the matrix. Sublayers of different nature and thickness (0.05–30 μm) were deposited on carbon and glass fibers by means of various techniques: from a solution; by electrodeposition from a fluidized bed; by coating the fiber in vacuum with the polymer dispersion using an electron gun. The bond strength was measured using the pull-out and fragmentation tests.

KEYWORDS: interphase, acid-base interactions, glass fibers, carbon fibers, fiber coating, micromechanical tests.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber sizing and coating are effective tools to control fiber-matrix interfacial interactions in polymer composites. Adhesion in boundary layers is determined not only by molecular interaction of the coupling agent with the fiber and the matrix, but also by the properties of the formed interphase, in particular, its thickness and strength. The design of interphases in composites requires separate investigation of different adhesion mechanisms.

In recent years, the importance of acid-base interaction at interfaces has been demonstrated. In particular, the correlation between interfacial strength and such thermodynamic parameters of the surface as enthalpy of adsorption [1–3] and free surface energy [1, 4–6] has been revealed. However, strong interfacial interaction is a necessary but not sufficient condition for good stress transfer between the matrix and the fibrous reinforcement. On the one hand, good adhesion between the fiber and the interphase can result in the failure through the interphase/matrix boundary [7]. On the other hand, deposition of chemically inactive sublayers, which prevent acid-base interactions, sometimes improves mechanical properties of composites, although the work of adhesion decreases [3, 8]. For instance, a ductile material is often introduced between the fiber and the matrix, which facilitates energy absorption under loading [9]. The latter is determined, to a great extent, by the thickness of the deposited

sublayer and the degree of matrix penetration into it (interdiffusion). At a sufficient diffusion level, an interpenetrating network (IPN) is formed, which is an important condition for good bonding between the interphase and the matrix. As a rule, there is an optimum interphase thickness; if the interphase is thicker, it becomes itself a "weak point", and the failure occurs *within* it [9, 10]. The existence of such a variety of factors which affect performance of interphases makes it necessary to investigate each particular mechanism and to take all them into account when designing composite interphases. In this paper, we try to analyze the effect of acid-base interactions at the interface as well as the thickness and chemical composition of artificial layer deposited using different techniques on the interfacial bond strength in thermoplastic polymer/thin fiber systems.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

PAN-based carbon fibers with a diameter of 7 μm and E-glass fibers with a diameter of 14 μm were used in the experiments. The matrices used were thermoplastic polymers: polystyrene (PS), poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF), polypropylene unmodified (PP) and maleic anhydride-grafted (PPM), high density polyethylene unmodified (PE) and modified by γ -radiation (PEM), poly-3,3-bis(chloromethyl)oxacyclobutane (PCB), polyamide 12 (PA), polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and Nylon 6, in the form of powders with particle size from 10 to 100 μm . The powders were dried before making specimens. As a coupling agent, γ -aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APS) was taken.

Deposition of sublayers

Interphases were created using several procedures.

- a). The APS sizing was applied from an aqueous solution within the continuous spinning process, immediately after glass fibers having been cooled.
- b). Thin PTFE sublayers were created by coating the fibers in vacuum with the polymer dispersed using an electron gun [11]. The layer thickness was measured by means of an electron microscope.
- c). "Thick" sublayers were obtained by electrodepositing powdered polymer onto fibers in the chamber of electrostatic fluidized bed coater [12].

Micromechanical tests

Pull-out test

These tests were carried out using a pull-out apparatus which allows high precision fiber displacement and force measurements as well as data management [13]. Single fibers were embedded in matrices in a separate micro-oven at a heating/cooling rate of about 50 K/min. The pull-out test was performed at a crosshead displacement rate of $1.2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mm/min. From each force-displacement curve, the force of debonding, F_d , and the embedded length, l_e , were determined and the apparent debonding shear strength, τ_{app} , for each specimen was calculated from the equation:

$$\tau_{app} = \frac{F_d}{\pi d l_e},$$

where d is the fiber diameter. The experimental relationship between τ_{app} and l_e was used to calculate the ultimate interfacial shear strength (IFSS), τ_{ult} , according to the algorithm

described in Ref. 14. The ultimate IFSS characterizes the bond strength between the fiber and the matrix and does not depend on specimen geometry [14, 15].

Fragmentation test

Single-fiber composites in the form of a dumbbell, with the fiber running along the specimen axis, were prepared as described in Refs. 12 and 16. The specimen stretching was performed on a tension testing machine at a strain rate of 0.2 mm/min until a neck of maximum possible length was reached. After that the specimen was released from the grips and the neck was examined in transmitted light in an optical microscope equipped with a calibrated eyepiece to measure fragment lengths. The electron microscope was used to check failure localization. The interfacial bond strength was calculated from Kelly's formula

$$\tau = C \frac{\overline{\sigma}_f d}{2\bar{l}},$$

where $\overline{\sigma}_f$ is the strength of the fiber of the mean fiber length \bar{l} , and C is the correction factor [17]. For carbon fibers used in this paper, its value appeared to be 0.94. As was demonstrated in Ref. 18, the interfacial bond strength determined using this technique is close to the τ_{ult} values from microbond and pull-out tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thin layers: acid-base interaction

As was shown by recent research, the interaction between acid and base sites (electron donor and acceptor groups) plays an important part in the phenomenon of adhesion; its contribution to the total bond strength and work of adhesion can be as great as the contribution of

Fig. 1: Zeta potential of unsized and γ -APS sized glass fibers as a function of pH.

(Fig. 1). Alteration of chemical nature of the fiber surface cannot substantially affect the adhesion of non-polar polymers, such as PP and PE, which is due to dispersion interaction only. The absence of polar groups in molecular structure of these polymers makes acid-base interaction (and, as a consequence, control over interfacial strength) impossible. Indeed,

dispersion forces [1–3, 19, 20]. Thus, the use of complementary donor and acceptor sites at the fiber surface and in the matrix material is the basis of molecular design of the interface.

Sizing of glass fibers with APS substantially alters the chemical nature of the surface: base amino groups take the place of acidic hydroxyl groups. The increase in the fiber basicity as a result of sizing can be seen, e.g., from markedly different electrokinetic characteristics of sized and unsized fibers

neither the work of adhesion (from inverse gas chromatography data, Table 1) nor the bond strength in the glass fiber/PP system changed on fiber sizing with APS (Fig. 2). Similar results have been obtained for PP matrix with cellulose fibers [3] and PE with glass fibers [8]:

Table 1: Effect of the fiber sizing on its adhesion to thermoplastic matrices

Matrix	Fiber sizing	τ_{ult} [MPa]	W_A [mJ/m ²]
PP	None	13	70
PP	APS	13	69
PPM	APS	23	103
PS	None	97	178
PS	APS	79	123
ABS	None	102	109
ABS	APS	83	88
Nylon 6	None	30*	81
Nylon 6	APS	88*	101

*From Ref. 23.

in considerable changes in both the work of adhesion and the bond strength in PP/sized glass fiber model composites (see Table 1). The reason for the improvement of adhesive interaction is formation of hydrogen (acid-base) bonds between base amino groups at the fiber surface and acidic carboxyl groups of the matrix. An important consequence is the increase in all strength components of corresponding composite materials: tensile strength, strength at three-point bending, and fracture toughness [21]. It should be mentioned that mechanical properties of the matrix are not changed on the modification, so that the whole effect can be with all reliability attributed to the interphase.

Another example of system in which acid-base interaction is improved as a result of fiber sizing with APS, is Nylon 6/glass fiber pair. Nylon 6, a polar polymer, contains acid groups, whose reaction with amino groups of the APS gives rise to the increase in the work of adhesion and the bond strength (Table 1), as well as in the strength of macro composites [8].

Fig. 2: The apparent debonding shear strength in glass fiber/polypropylene matrix as a function of embedded length.

both W_A and composite strength were the same for sized and unsized fibers.

The control over interfacial interaction in the case of non-polar polymers is only possible provided that both the fiber surface and the matrix are being modified simultaneously. Since APS sizing imparts base properties to the fiber surface, acid groups must be introduced into the polymer. Indeed, matrix modification with maleic anhydride, as described in Ref. 21, results

On the contrary, for polar polymers which are electron donors, the intensity of acid-base interaction at the fiber/matrix boundary should decrease after fiber sizing with base agents. As can be seen in Table 1, ABS and PS, containing predominantly donor groups (phenyl, vinyl, nitrile) show better adhesion to unsized fibers. The deposited APS covers hydroxyl ($-OH$) groups present at the glass fiber surface and depresses their interaction with polar groups of the polymers; as a result, the bond strength decreases (Fig. 3, a, b). These results

Fig. 3: The apparent debonding shear strength in glass fiber/ABS (a) and glass fiber/PS (b) matrix as a function of embedded length.

agree with those reported in Ref. 22 where the strength of APS/glass fiber composites in tension and three-point bending has been shown to be deteriorated after fiber treatment with a silane sizing.

Thick layers: interdiffusion

Deposition of "thick" polymer layers on fibers makes diffusion or entanglement of polymer chains to the main mechanism of bonding. This mechanism also can be successfully used in the interphase design. For example, in the "dry" technology of plastics production, the sublayer in the form of tiny particles is deposited in an electric field from a fluidized bed, after which the main matrix material (also powdered) is added. Bond strength measurement for various carbon-fiber/ sublayer/ matrix systems using the fragmentation test showed that in all cases it was intermediate between cor-

Table 2: Bond strength in carbon fiber/electrodeposited sublayer/polymer matrix systems

Matrix	Sublayer	Thermal treatment conditions $T, ^\circ\text{C} / t, \text{min}$	Bond strength [MPa]		
			matrix only	sublayer only	sublayer +matrix
PVDF	PC	270/60	32	79	52
PVDF	PCB	270/60	32	8.9	15
PP	PCB*	225/15	6.2	36	20
PCB	PA	225/15	8.9	118	22
PP	PA	225/15	6.2	118	26
PCB*	PP	225/15	36	6.2	27
PE	PE**	200/15	21	43	38

*Partially crystallized.

**Modified by gamma radiation.

responding values for the matrix and sublayer materials (Table 2). It should be mentioned that in all cases one of two polymer materials (either the matrix or the sublayer) was non-polar; therefore, it was difficult to expect any acid-base interaction at the interphase/matrix boundary. Thus, every change in the bond strength can be attributed to polymer interdiffusion and entanglement of polymer chains. When creating interphases using this technique,

Fig. 3: Bond strength in the carbon fiber/PTFE sublayer/PC matrix system as a function of the sublayer thickness.

while at the sublayer-matrix boundary interdiffusion plays the main part. As a result, the efficiency of the load transfer doubles as against the composite without a sublayer (see Table 2).

Additional information about the type and localization of failure in model thermoplastic polymer/coated fiber composites can be obtained by investigation of the bond strength in the system as a function of the sublayer thickness. For this purpose, we coated carbon fibers with PTFE in vacuum using an electron gun. In Fig. 3, the bond strength, τ , in carbon fiber/PC system is plotted *versus* the thickness, h , of PTFE sublayer. At small coating thickness ($<0.1 \mu\text{m}$), the bond strength increased as compared with carbon fibers without coating, but further increase of the thickness results in fast interfacial strength decrease and its stabilization at the level of $46 \pm 4 \text{ MPa}$. The presence of a maximum in the $\tau(h)$ plot evidences the change in the mechanism of interfacial failure with increased sublayer thickness. In all probability, PTFE, activated by an electron flow, contains many active sites and therefore shows good adhesion to both PC and carbon fibers. At the same time, cohesive strength of PTFE even decreases under the electron beam action, since high-energy electrons cause breaks of C–C bonds in the main polymer chain. Therefore, very thin PTFE coating acts as adhesive and improves bond strength between the fibers and polycarbonate. The increase of the layer thickness results in alteration of the mechanism of interfacial failure from debonding to interphase shear. The bond strength gradually diminishes and then remains constant: at $h > 0.2 \mu\text{m}$, the interphase is the "weak point" of the system, and measured effective interfacial shear strength is the shear strength of the interphase.

CONCLUSION

For polar polymers, the strength of both micro- and macrocomposites is determined, to a considerable extent, by acid-base interactions at the interface. A correlation was revealed between the work of adhesion, estimated from inverse gas chromatography data, and the interfacial bond strength. In the case of non-polar polymers, the bond strength can be

diffusion is facilitated by the fact that the process of interphase formation takes place for a sufficiently long time and at the temperature which is above melting points of both polymers.

As a rule, in most real interphases the two mechanisms of bonding are competitive. This can be exemplified by a sublayer of polyethylene modified by gamma radiation. Its good adhesion to fiber surface is due to the presence of active groups involved in acid-base interactions at the interface,

controlled only by means of simultaneous modification of the matrix and the fiber, i.e. creation of complementary acid and base sites on the two contacting surfaces. Diffusion in the interphase plays an important role; it provides "continuity" between the fiber and the matrix. At poor diffusion, the interphase itself or its boundary with the main matrix material becomes the "weak point" of the composite.

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